

Predict Star Rating from Review text

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ABSTRACT

Reviews play an important role to understand information about event, place or any commercial product. These reviews are captured simply on the numeric scale or it can be an elaborated details text review. In this study, we analyze if we can summarize the big textual review by predicting stars using information retrieval and machine learning. We also perform sentiment analysis to understand if the sentiments in the review are in accordance with the star rating provided. Our findings show that star rating can be predicted to some extent based on the review comments. The sentiment present in review some time doesn't match with the star rating provided for the review. This model can be enhanced further to add more features to improve the accuracy which will be beneficial to summarize the review comment to the star rating and save people time to read through the entire review description.

KEYWORDS

Yelp, Information Retrieval, Reviews, Sentiment Analysis, Classification

1 INTRODUCTION

In this digital era where almost everything can be purchased online, review of a product not only helps the user to make the buying decision but also helps companies to understand users view and strategies accordingly. All big retailers like Amazon, eBay, WalMart, etc provides a capability for the user to provide the review comment and rate product based on the star scale rating. However, star scale rating and detailed review text have their own pros and cons. The text review can be detailed and elaborated which provides a user with a lot of finer details to make the decision but it is also time-consuming to go through all those details. On the other hand, the star rating is a quick way to summarize the overall review but will not provide finer details which are available in the detailed review. User point of view sometimes it's easy to just go through the star ratings and make the decision instead of going through the entire review. This study's one of the goal is to understand if we can find out star rating if we have review text is available.

Another aspect is about understanding sentiment present in the review text which is quite helpful to the companies as they can identify and focus such reviews to improve their products or resolve users issues. It would be interesting to know if the sentiment present in the review matches with the star rating provided. Is it true that higher star rating means positive sentiment and lower star rating means negative sentiments? In this study, we investigate if the reviewer's star rating matches with the sentiment expressed in the review.

Yelp [11] provide a platform to connect people with the business. It has millions of reviews along with star rating by people on various businesses. In this study, we utilize this quality data to understand if the star rating can be predicted based on the review text. We strive to understand if the sentiment expressed in the Yelp reviews matches with the star rating provided.

In the next section, we review work carried out on similar problem followed by the methodology used for this study. We then publish results in detail and finally conclude this study based on our findings.

2 RELATED WORK

Several works have been published addressing Yelp review rating prediction. Most of the work related to Yelp review rating prediction is based on sentiment analysis to extract features from the review text. Ordenes et al. propose a framework for linguistic text-mining for deep analysis of customer experience [6]. Pang and Lee utilized text mining to extract sentimental insights from customer data to improve customer loyalty measurement [7]. Qu et al. (2010) proposed a novel feature extraction method called bag-of-opinions, where opinion in a review is made of a root word, negation word and a set of modifier words from the same sentence. Each opinion is assigned a score and review's rating is predicted by aggregating the scores of opinions and combining it with a domain dependent unigram model [8]. Ganu et al. (2009) developed techniques to classify and analyze text- and structure-based web reviews, and use analysis to improve personalized recommendations for web users. Their approach involves combining natural language processing, machine learning and collaborative filtering [2].

Boya yu et al. [13], in their study suggest how sentiment analysis of the review can be helpful in identifying restaurant features. Isa Maks & Piek Vossen [4] suggests that reader's rating are more reliable than the reviewer's ratings based on the sentiment analysis.

3 DATA AND METHODS

We followed the step by step approach as shown in the process diagram (Figure 1) to analyze and publish the results of the study.

We identified Yelp as our data source which has a rich dataset of review comments and star ratings. We collected data in a JSON format from the Yelp website and added an index to it for the faster information retrieval purpose. We then constructed queries to retrieve the data and that data is used for exploratory analysis. We further used this data for the semantic analysis and developed a machine learning model to classify the review for a start rating. In the final step of this process, we published the results and conclusion of the study.

Figure 1: Methodology

3.1 Dataset

Data were obtained in JSON data format from Yelp Dataset Challenge round 13. Yelp has different JSON files like business.json, review.json, user.json, tip.json. Yelp dataset is readily available and is in well-structured JSON format. This is a large dataset almost 8GB in size which will help draw good insights in terms of business usage or user behavior. This data set is used by numerous user to solve data challenges published by Yelp. The dataset review.json used in our research is the driving dataset for the problem we are trying to solve. It contains full review text data including the user that wrote the review and the business for which review is written [12]. The total number of records for the review.json dataset is 66,85,900. Figure 2 shows attribute details and data format for review.json Overall data quality of attributes in perspective of completeness:

Attributes	Datatype	Description
review_id	String	22-character unique review id
user_id	String	22-character unique user id
business_id	String	22-character business id
stars	integer	star rating
date	String	date formatted YYYY-MM-DD
text	String	Review itself
useful	integer	number of useful votes received
funny	integer	number of funny votes received
cool	integer	number of cool votes received

```

{
  "review_id": "Q1sbwvQXV2734tPgokj4Q",
  "user_id": "hg7b0MtEbX5QzbE6C_VA",
  "business_id": "ujmEBvifdJM6h6RLv4wQlg",
  "stars": 1.0,
  "useful": 6,
  "funny": 1,
  "cool": 0,
  "text": "Total bill for this horrible service? Over $8Gs. These crooks actually",
  "date": "2013-05-07 04:34:36"
}
  
```

Figure 2: Data attributes and format

- Attributes which were the point of focus for research were stars and text
- All records had values in attributes stars and text
- Stars has either one of values from integer 5,4,3,2,1
- Text attribute had no empty string or null values
- All records had key's stars and text
- Values in text attribute had characters like @, #,!,?,spaces

3.2 Data Cleaning

Yelp data text attribute had characters like @, #, !, ?, spaces. These characters don't add any value in the classification or sentiment analysis process but may add bias in overall analysis so we cleaned this data by using the process as follows.

- (1) Removed unnecessary spaces after # and @
- (2) Removed null strings
- (3) Dropped empty strings
- (4) Removed @, #,!,?
- (5) Converted all uppercase letters to lowercase

3.3 Information Retrieval

The information retrieval is a crucial part of such data centric project as we want fast data retrieval as well as an ability to select data of our interest. We identified user information and review information from Yelp dataset as a piece of crucial information for this study. We used Apache Lucene [1] libraries to create index on the user and review dataset for the fast retrieval. We also wanted to consider reviews which are written and rated correctly. This data selection is important as it will give us a reliable dataset which would be useful in our machine learning and sentiment analysis process to improve accuracy. We decided to consider reviews of the users who have submitted reviews at least 1000 times so that we get quality reviews for our analysis. We used range query to select users who have submitted more than 1000 reviews. We first selected all such users from the user dataset and then we retrieved all review comments along with the star rating for all those users from the user-review dataset. This process helped us with size-able quality data for the semantic and classification analysis.

3.4 Classification

Our research was performed to answer two questions:

1. Do user's reviews resonate what user rated on Yelp?
2. Can we predict rating based on user's review?

In our research, the results of question 1 are very critical as it provides a base for correct prediction. Typically, with text limitations on microblogging site users tend to put important and crisp text to convey the message. But Yelp allows users to write free text with no limitations, unlike Twitter which only allows 140-character limit. So, it is imperative to evaluate the results of question 1. If reviews resonate user rating than end users can rely on rating's and does not have to read entire review comments before taking any decision. Additionally, reviews can be used to predict Business rating. Based on Data analysis we concluded that stars can have either one of the values from integer bucket of 5,4,3,2 or 1. Each review text has star rating assigned to it hence text feature is labeled with stars. So, research can be categorized as a supervised classification problem and metrics used to evaluate is accuracy.

3.5 Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis is useful for understanding the sentiment expressed in the text. This can be useful information for our analysis as review comments certainly will have sentiment expressed either as bad, good, angry, neutral etc. The expectation is, sentiment in the review will be as per the star rating provided by the user. The reviews with a star rating 4 or 5 should be positive and the rating 1

or 2 should be negative. The rating with star 3 might be mixed or neutral. We want to study if this expectation is true or not and if it can be used in predicting the star rating.

We used *TextBlob* [10] and *Afinn* [5] package to perform our sentiment analysis. The *Textblob* package provides a polarity score based on the text. If the score is greater than 0 then the text has positive sentiments and if the score is less than 0 then it has a negative sentiment. If the polarity score is 0 then it is considered as a neutral sentiment. Similarly, *Afinn* is a knowledge-based lexicon which has over 3000 word list with the polarity score attached [3]. If the polarity score is positive then the text has positive sentiment and if the score is negative then it has negative sentiment or else it is neutral. We used both packages to derive the polarity score for the review text and based on the polarity score we classified it as either positive, negative or neutral. We then did exploratory analysis to find out if sentiments are in accordance with the star rating or not.

4 RESULTS

In this section, we will discuss results and observation from our study.

4.1 Information Retrieval

The indexing of Yelp data provided us with some statistic in terms of the number of user and reviews present in the data. The dataset contains total 1,637,138 (more than a million) user and 6,685,900 (more than 6 million) reviews. We identified 1,426 (one thousand, four hundred and twenty-six) users who have provided reviews at least 1000 times. We selected total 133,746 review records based on those users. We only considered star rating and review text from those review record for our further study. Figure 3 shows review distribution by the star rating from the data generated through the information retrieval process.

Figure 3: Review Distribution By Star Rating

4.2 Data Exploration

The data retrieved from the information retrieval process has very uneven distribution as shown in figure 3. The dataset is dominated by rating 4 reviews followed by rating 3. There is very less number of reviews for rating 1 and 2. This uneven distribution is not much helpful for our machine learning and sentiment analysis process

as it may add bias. We decided to make our distribution even by selecting an equal number (10k) of records for each star rating. Figure 4 shows review distribution by star rating after equal number of records selected for each star. We still have less number of record for review with the star rating 1.

Figure 4: Equal Review Distribution By Star Rating

4.3 Classification

Comparison of different Algorithms was performed using 3-fold cross-validation. As seen in figure 5, the Logistic Regression Classifier outperformed the others with a mean accuracy of 50.42%. SVC under-performed versus the other algorithms with a mean accuracy of 22.56%. Figure 5 shows a boxplot of the accuracy performance of each algorithm to demonstrate the distributions of accuracy scores. Although these are subjectively acceptable accuracy scores,

Figure 5: ML Base Accuracy

we believed that they can be improved using hyperparameter tuning (or hyperparameter optimization). Hyperparameter tuning is the method of adjusting parameters from their default to achieve improved predictive accuracy. To accomplish this, we used the methods from the scikit-learn documentation [9]. By implementing these techniques, we improved our accuracy for several algorithms. Figure 6 shows results for all our experiments with different machine learning algorithms used for this study. Tuned SVC has shown the best accuracy of 52.03%.

ExpID	Accuracy	Experiment description
0	SVC 0.225617	No Tuning
2	Naive Bayes 0.482587	No Tuning
3	Logistic Regression 0.504288	No Tuning
4	RandonForest Classifier 0.383733	No Tuning
5	DecisionTreeClassifier 0.326561	No Tuning
6	SVC(Tuned) 0.5203	Tuned parameter={'C': 10, 'gamma': 1}
7	Naive Bayes 0.4851	Naive Bayesmodel
8	Log reg Tuned 0.5104	Tuned parameter={'C': 1, 'penalty': 'l1'}

Figure 6: Classification Accuracy

4.4 Sentiment Analysis

In this section, we document our results from sentiment analysis carried out on the review text. We observe that for certain star rating sentiments are matching but at the same time there are mixed sentiments which don't match with the star rating. This also proves that user may not be providing star rating as per their review comment or long review text which includes both positive and negative points in the review might be confusing to deduce correct sentiment by the sentiment analysis packages.

4.4.1 *Text Blob*. Figure 7 shows review text sentiment comparison as per the star rating based on TextBlob analysis. It shows most of the reviews as positive sentiments for the star rating 4 and 5 which is as expected but some user has rated high but the sentiment is not positive. Contrary to our expectation star rating 1 and 2 are having a lot of positive sentiments which is not expected. Star rating 3 is also showing a lot of positive sentiments instead of neutral sentiments.

Figure 7: Textblob sentiments by star ratings

4.4.2 *Afinn*. Figure 8 shows review text sentiment comparison as per the star rating based on Afinn analysis. It also shows similar results as TextBlob package but performs better in terms of detecting negative sentiment for star rating 1.

Figure 8: Afinn sentiments by star ratings

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we used review data from Yelp to understand if rating classification can be done based on the review text and sentiments in the review text is matching with the star rating or not. We observed that, a model can be developed which can classify star rating based on the review description but has bit lower accuracy. Provision of unlimited text in Yelp can be one of the factors for lower accuracy as the user tries to cover all positive and negative aspects which create confusion for the classifier to predict correctly. It is also possible that users are not providing star rating as per the details provided in the review. The sentiment analysis also suggests that sentiment present in the review is not matching with the rating provided as we see positive reviews but with lower star rating.

6 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have not used multiple n-grams in this study which can be useful to generate good features for our machine learning classifier and help improve accuracy. We can use topic modeling technique such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation for feature extraction. We have used evaluation KPI as Accuracy only, but for more detailed performance evaluation, we can try other metrics, such as precision, recall, F-score and confusion matrix. One of the limitations which we consistently encountered was limited memory while training the dataset. We can use Cloud-based services like AWS Sagemaker which will provide elasticity in terms of compute nodes. We performed 3-fold cross-validation in our experiments because 10-fold cross validation was very expensive in terms of time and memory. It would be worthwhile to evaluate 10-fold cross-validation and check if it yields different results. This can be achieved by cloud-based services which provides greater computing capability.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Apache. 2019. Welcome to Apache Lucene. web. (2019). <http://lucene.apache.org/>
- [2] Gayatree Ganu, No'Almie Elhadad, and Am'Alie Marian. [n. d.]. Beyond the Stars: Improving Rating Predictions using Review Text Content. ([n. d.]).

- [3] Himanshu Lohiya. 2018. Sentiment Analysis with AFINN Lexicon. Web Page. (July 2018). https://medium.com/@himanshu_23732/sentiment-analysis-with-afinn-lexicon-930533dfe75b
- [4] Isa Maks and Piek T. J. M. Vossen. 2013. Sentiment Analysis of Reviews: Should we analyze writer intentions or reader perceptions?. In *RANLP*.
- [5] Neuro. 2019. AFINN. web. (2019). <http://neuro.compute.dtu.dk/wiki/AFINN>
- [6] Theodoulidis B. Burton J. Gruber T. Zaki M. Ordenes, F. V. 2014. Analyzing Customer Experience Feedback Using Text Mining: A Linguistics-Based Approach. web. (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094670514524625>
- [7] Bo Pang and Lillian Lee. 2008. Opinion Mining and Sentiment Analysis. *Found. Trends Inf. Retr.* 2, 1-2 (Jan. 2008), 1–135. <https://doi.org/10.1561/15000000011>
- [8] Lizhen Qu, Georgiana Ifrim, and Gerhard Weikum. 2010. The Bag-of-opinions Method for Review Rating Prediction from Sparse Text Patterns. In *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING '10)*. Association for Computational Linguistics, Stroudsburg, PA, USA, 913–921. <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1873781.1873884>
- [9] scikit. 2019. Parameter estimation using grid search with cross-validation. web. (2019). https://scikit-learn.org/stable/auto_examples/model_selection/plot_grid_search_digits.html
- [10] TextBlob. 2019. TextBlob. web. (2019). <https://textblob.readthedocs.io/en/dev/quickstart.html#sentiment-analysis>
- [11] Yelp. 2019. Yelp. web. (2019). <https://www.yelp.com/>
- [12] Yelp. 2019. Yelp Dataset JSON. web. (2019). <https://www.yelp.com/dataset/documentation/main>
- [13] Boya Yu, Jiaxu Zhou, Yi Zhang, and Yunong Cao. 2017. Identifying Restaurant Features via Sentiment Analysis on Yelp Reviews. (09 2017).